

representatives, diplomatic ranks, diplomatic papers, diplomatic procedures, diplomatic visits, diplomatic missions, diplomatic rights and privileges of diplomatic receptions, among others.

Thus, comprehensive encyclopedic knowledge, internal culture, interaction experience and continual diplomatic training all contribute to intercultural communication efficacy in the diplomatic realm.

USED LITERATURE:

1. Diplomatiicheskiy slovar / Otv. red. A. A. Gromyko. T. 1. – M.: Nauka, 1984. – S. 327.
2. Heinrich Wildner: The technique of diplomacy. Springer, Vienna 1959. – 252 p.
3. The Oxford English Dictionary.1989. Publisher: Oxford University Press. UK. London. – 585 p.

THE RELEVANCE OF INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION IN MODERN CONDITIONS

Khakimova Munira Khabibullayevna

senior teacher of

Tashkent University of Applied Sciences, Tashkent

Annotation: This article is devoted to intercultural communication which is actual nowadays. Scientific and technological progress and the efforts of a rational and peace-loving part of humanity are opening up new opportunities, types and forms of communication, the main condition for the effectiveness of which is mutual understanding, dialogue of cultures, tolerance and respect for the culture of communication partners.

Key words: implicitly, explicitly, immemorial, folk wisdom, generation, transmitted, culturological, mentality, social behavior

The importance of all cultural topics as gained a previously unparalleled intensity, relevance of all issues related to culture, has acquired an unprecedented urgency. Increased curiosity in researching various nations' cultures of different nations, bringing to the forefront of culture, which only recently erased a miserable existence in the margins of history, philosophy, philology; her selection in a scientific specialty. In recent years, social, political and economic shocks of a global scale have led to an unprecedented migration of peoples, their resettlement, clash, confusion, which, of course, leads to a conflict of cultures. At the same time, scientific and technological progress and the efforts of a rational and peace-loving part of humanity are opening up new opportunities, types and forms of communication, the main condition for the effectiveness of which is mutual understanding, dialogue of cultures, tolerance and respect for the culture of communication partners.

All this taken together - both alarming and encouraging - and has led to especially close attention to issues of intercultural communication. However, these questions are eternal, they have worried humanity since time immemorial. As evidence, let us recall one proverb. Proverbs rightly consider clots of folk wisdom, that is, that same cultural experience that is stored in the language and transmitted from generation to generation. According to E. Sepir, "every cultural system and every single act of social behavior explicitly or implicitly implies communication" [1,p.21].

Thus, we are already talking about the need for a deeper and more thorough study of the world (not the language, but also the media) of the speakers language, their culture in the broad ethnographic sense of the word, their way of life, national character, mentality, etc., because the real use of words in speech, real speech reproduction is largely determined by knowledge of the social and cultural life of the speech community speaking a given language. "Language does not exist outside of culture, that is, outside of a socially inherited set of practical skills and

ideas that characterize our way of life". Linguistic structures are based on sociocultural structures [2,p.185].

Types and forms of intercultural communication are rapidly developing. In a completely different field, such as medicine, the same law applies: it is better not to go to a foreign body with its charter / treatment. Since it is necessary to treat not the disease, but the patient, the treatment must take into account both the individual characteristics of the patient and the national-cultural features of his behavior, psychology, worldview, habitual environment, etc. The great Avicenna (Ibn Sina) a thousand years ago taught back that "if you give the Indian a Slavic nature, then the Indian will fall ill or even die. The same will happen with the Slav, if he is given the nature of an Indian"[3,p.353].

Obviously, by "nature" we mean national culture. Books forbidden (or burned at the stake) by one or another political regime vividly (the brighter the more bonfires) indicate a conflict of ideologies, the incompatibility of cultures (including within the same national culture). Of course, the reading of foreign authors is an invasion of a foreign monastery. We see and, most importantly, evaluate this alien world through the prism of our culture, which, accordingly, also turns out to be a conflict of culture. E. M. Vereshchagin and V. G. Kostomarov, fathers of linguistic and regional studies in Russia, formulated this most important aspect of language teaching as follows: "Two national cultures never completely coincide," this follows from the fact that each consists of national and international elements. The sets of coinciding (international) and diverging (national) units for each pair of comparable cultures will be different ... Therefore, we are talking about the inclusion of elements of regional geography in language teaching, but this is a qualitatively different kind of inclusion compared to general geography. Since we are talking about combining language and information from the sphere of national culture in the educational process, this type of teaching work is proposed to be called linguistic and regional teaching" [4,p.30].

In linguistics, a comprehensive study of the interaction of language and culture was formed in the nineteenth century. The foundations of the culturological and

ethnolinguistic approach to the study of language were laid in the works of W. von Humboldt, who believed that “language is the world that lies between the world of external phenomena and the inner world of man”[5,p.349].

To sum up, in such an explosive situation, science and education face complex and noble tasks: firstly, to study the roots, manifestations, forms, types, development of cultures of different peoples and their contacts, and secondly, to teach people tolerance, respect, understanding of other cultures. To accomplish this task, conferences are held, associations of scientists and teachers are created, books are written, cultural studies are introduced in the curricula of both secondary and higher educational institutions. Of particular importance is the solution (or at least awareness) of the problems of intercultural communication for teaching foreign languages.

REFERENCES:

1. Sepir E. Kommunikatsia. Izbranniye trudi po yazikoznaniyu i kulturologii, p.21
2. Sepir E. Yazik. Vvedeniye v izucheniya rechi. // Izbranniye trudi po yazikoznaniyu i kulturologii, p.185.
3. Mudroye slovo o Drevney Rusi., 1989, - p. 353.
4. Vereshchagin E.M., Kostomarov V.G., Ukaz sochineniy, - p. 30.
5. Gumboldt W. fon. “Yazik I filosofiya kulturi”, - 1985, s. 349.
6. Vereshchagin E.M., Kostomarov V.G., Ukaz sochineniy, - p. 30.
7. Talabovna, S. S. (2022). Features of English and Uzbek comparisons in linguocultural aspect. international journal of social science & interdisciplinary research ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11(11), 424-429.
8. Sodiqova, S. (2021). The implementation of speaking strategies in developing students' communicative competence. Журнал иностранных языков и лингвистики, 2(4).